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**WHEATBIOME – Unraveling the potential of the wheat microbiome
for the development of healthier, more sustainable and resilient
wheat-derived food & feed products**

**DELIVERABLE D8.2
DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN**

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Dissemination Level	
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PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for member of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Leader partner for this deliverable: REQUIMTE

Document status and versions

Version	Date	Description
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Data Management Plan (DMP) provides an overview of all datasets collected and generated by the WHEATBIOME project and defines the WHEATBIOME consortium's data management policy with regard to these datasets.

The WHEATBIOME DMP follows the structure of the Horizon Europe DMP template [1]. It reflects the status of the data that is collected, processed, or generated, and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.

This initial version of the DMP defines the general policy and approach to data management within WHEATBIOME, addressing administrative and technical data management issues. This includes topics such as data and meta-data collection, publication and deposition of open data, the data repository infrastructure, and Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) compliance.

It also summarizes the guidelines on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data management [2]. Future versions will refine and improve policy aspects and provide more information about the datasets collected and generated by the WHEATBIOME project.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	5
1. DATA SUMMARY	6
2. FAIR DATA	9
2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	10
2.2 Making data accessible	10
2.3 Making data interoperable	12
2.4 Making data re-use	12
3. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS	13
4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	16
5. DATA SECURITY	16
6. ETHICS	16

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Table 1. Designation of the abbreviations or acronyms used and the corresponding description

Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
DMP	Data Management Plan
IRP	Intellectual Property Rights
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
O365	Microsoft Office 365

Table 2. Partner short-name used in this document and the correspondent's full name

Partner short-name	Full partner name
REQUIMTE	Rede de Química e Tecnologia - Associação
UVIGO	Universidade de Vigo
UPORTO	Universidade do Porto
UVEG	Universitat de València-Estudi General
IBPRS	Instytut Biotechnologii Przemysłu Rolno-Spożywczego
CTA	Contactica S. L.
WR	Wageningen Research
SGGW	Szkoła Główna Gospodarstwa Wiejskiego
NMS	Nova Medical School
UVMB	Állatorvostudományi Egyetem
EDAGRI	Editorial Agrícola Española S.A.
ART21	ART21 Ltd
ISANATUR	ISANATUR Spain S.L.

1. DATA SUMMARY

The assessment of the role of the wheat microbiome on the development of new sustainable, nutritious and healthy food and feed will necessitate the collection, processing, and storage of a vast array of data sets related to the entire chain of food and feed production, including general environmental and meteorological variables, agricultural practices, several research data sets related but not limited to nutritional characterization (quantitative and qualitative), consumer queries, etc.

As data identification and collection activities are at their very beginning, the initial DMP can only provide a partial picture of the datasets required for the various Work Packages within the WHEATBIOME project. In spite of this, the current data summary provides a fair overview of the various types of datasets required for the input of models and tools in WHEATBIOME project.

While the first version of the DMP focuses primarily on data collected or to be collected, the next version will also report on data produced as part of the project as well as non-sensitive data that can be made publicly accessible in open data repositories and registered at pertinent catalogs. On the one hand, data will come from a combination of already-existing databases, results from past and ongoing national and European programs, and a review of the literature (sources: SCOPUS, Web of Science, PubMed, ScienceDirect, etc.) (reused data) to convey all data regarding the knowledge on the link between microbiome and soil, wheat plant and grain quality, resilience, sustainability and agricultural practices. These data will be included in Word files (.docx), Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx), EndNote Clarivates files (.enl) and/or text files (.txt).

Data corresponding to the sampling on wheat fields from each case-study will be also collected, such as location, classification of soil, climate, property, crop history, land management and agricultural practices (plot characteristics, treatment applied, management practices, sampling and analyses) (WP1&WP2). These data will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx).

We will compile stakeholders' contacts, information and into Word (.docx) and Excel files (.xlsx). Due to the sensitive information about individuals, this information will never be made public or accessible; instead, it will only be used by project partners to further the project's goals before being permanently deleted. It will only be used internally and shared on Teams.

The new data/research output will be generated during the WHEATBIOME project within WP1 to WP5. These will be in the form of laboratory notebooks, text documents and spreadsheets (e.g., experimental procedures), database content (massive processing of data), documented methodologies and workflows, among others. The overall data generated

will be then collected as databases, spreadsheets with collected data, and reports with variants in each case scenario (experimental data).

New data will derive from soil, wheat plant and grain analysis (WP1). Selected indicators for characterization of soil composition (pH, organic matter/total carbon content, trace elements content, texture, etc), wheat nutritional, quality parameters and overall metabolism (total content of protein, lipid, carbohydrate, fiber, immunogenic proteins, bioactive compounds, etc) will be measured for the samples collected in each case-study. These data will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). WP1 will also produce new DNA sequencing data of soil and wheat plant biological communities, that will be stored in .bam and .fastq files, which can be operated with the open access R software.

Statistical analysis and multi-factor comparative analysis of all the collected results (WP1&WP2) is one of the cornerstones of WHEATBIOME since multiple variants have an important role in the continuation of the project and adaptation of the suggested actions. These data will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx) and can be operated by XLSTAT or SPSS software (.sav).

New data will derive from fermentation experiments to produce novel foods in WP3. Selected indicators for key fermentation parameters (pH, counting of colony forming unit, etc) will be measured to optimize fermentation conditions. In addition, the resulting food proof-of-concepts will be characterized from nutritional (total content of protein, lipid, etc), quality (immunogenic proteins, antioxidant capacity, etc) and safety perspectives (mycotoxins, biogenic amines, etc). All these data will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). WP3 will also produce new DNA sequencing data of novel microorganisms used in fermentation, that will be stored in .bam and .fastq files.

New data will derive from the validation of the novel fermented wheat-based food products in WP4. Selected indicators for bioaccessibility and digestibility parameters (bioactive compounds and peptides determination/identification, etc), interaction of food with human microbiota (aggregation ability), impact on intestinal barrier and its function (inflammatory response) will be measured. In addition, the resulting new fermented foods will be also evaluated by surveys/questionnaires by consumers regarding risk perception and preferences as well as sensory acceptance. Data will be handled in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). Data from the clinical trial will include determination of several biological parameters (glucose, lipid profile, hepatic enzymes, microbiota characterization, etc) which will be gathered in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx).

New data will derive from the development of novel fermented wheat-based feed products in WP5. Selected indicators for best fermentation conditions, characterization of the nutritional

profile of feed and safety, and feed products validation (similar to WP3 & WP4) will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx).

Data generated from Life Cycle Assessment and the economic valuation (WP6) will be gathered in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx) to identify real economic benefits of the novel fermented production (WP3).

Overall, WHEATBIOME will produce a variety of datasets, but the majority of them will be numerical and, to a lesser extent, text as a consequence of various surveys and questionnaires, as well as images for mapping and network planning. The majority of the data sets will be made up of observational data (experimental design data, surveys and questionnaires, economic and financial assessment, and decision support system), experimental data recorded by field and laboratory equipment, and simulation data (decision support system models used to evaluate the performance of digital application in WP2).

Regarding the size of the generated data, there will be a fair number of datasets generated, but none will be very large, allowing them to be compiled on spreadsheets for simple accessibility.

2. FAIR DATA

The project is essentially divided into the nine work packages listed below:

- WP1: Study of the factors influencing the microbiomes & attributes of wheat in different areas of Europe
- WP2: Integrative multi-factor evaluation of the influence of soil and plant microbiota on wheat crops
- WP3: New wheat-based microbial-derived food products
- WP4: Validation of novel fermented wheat-based food products
- WP5: Development of cutting-edge fermented poultry feeds
- WP6: Sustainability assessment of the novel wheat-based food and feed fermented production
- WP7: Exploitation, Communication and Dissemination
- WP8: Project Management
- WP9: Ethics requirements

Of these nine work packages, WP1, WP3, WP4, and WP5 will be the most technically oriented and focus on the physical-chemical characterization of soil and wheat (plant and grain), on the characterization of soil and wheat microbiomes, as well as on the the development of new food and feed products, aligned with the screening of specific bioactivities and the soil-plant-food-host microbial interactions. Additionally, WP2 will focus on developing tools for evaluation and decision-making based on the inputs from the most technical WP.

An analysis of the potential environmental sustainability and economic feasibility will be done within WP6. Additionally, WP7 will focus on maximizing the impact through the Exploitation, Communication, and Dissemination of the project results to the different stakeholders involved in wheat production and transformation.

The primary project outputs are the deliverables listed in Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A, which will take mainly the form of reports. However, some of the deliverables will be surveys as well prototypes of new food or feed.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The multidisciplinary nature of the project concludes in a varied datasets collected. Namely, the microbial diversity of the fields, the meteorological and agronomic conditions, the agronomic practices, the different microbial communities tested to obtain specific fermentation conditions, which further affect the food and feed nutritional quality and probiotic and bioactive compounds profile....

Under this context, the metadata standard used to describe the dataset will be the Dublin Core Schema, as it is a flexible and commonly used standard and is also the one adopted by the European OpenAIRE repository, which will be used. The Community “WHEATBIOME” will be created within Zenodo to increase the efficiency when finding the data of this project. The depositors will create the metadata manually when uploading the datasets to Zenodo. Additionally, specific keywords will also be manually added to each dataset uploaded to Zenodo to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential reuse. These keywords will be provided based on the expertise of the depositors, who are familiar with the most commonly used keywords in their field. Furthermore, the datasets will include some tabs or pages with description of data factors and variable names and units.

2.2 Making data accessible

All datasets supporting publications will be made openly and publicly available on the OpenAire repository Zenodo upon acceptance of the manuscript for publication. For this, the Community “WHEATBIOME” will be created. Moreover, all datasets generated along the project work plan will be made public three years after completion of the project, and after data publishing through proper manuscripts, which will be published in the primary journals of the areas of agriculture, food, feed, chemistry and related subjects. The repository Zenodo assigns a DOI for persistent identification and citability of the dataset. The Project dataset identification follows the naming:

WHEATBIOME_<WPno>_<serial number of dataset>_<dataset title>_<versionnumber(date)>.

All datasets will be uploaded to the WHEATBIOME Community of Zenodo for easy and rapid finding.

The data gathered by partners complementary but outside the project work plan and protected by intellectual property rights (IPR), or inside the work plan but containing confidential information (e.g. related to personal interviews, stakeholder's contact information), will be kept closed for privacy reasons.

Data will be shared among members of work packages continuously as they are being generated, by using the WHEATBIOME Teams library associated to the O365 platform of tools for collaborative work (online platform belonging to beneficiary), as referred in the Project Management Plan (deliverable 8.1). Furthermore, when a dataset turns openly accessible, it will be announced on the web page of the WHEATBIOME project <https://www.wheatbiome-project.eu/>, where a link to the dataset on Zenodo will be available in order to improve the metadata dissemination and accessibility.

The vast majority of the datasets will be made available as spreadsheets (.xlsx format) and to a lesser extent as .pdf, .ppt, .txt, .csv, .enl, .docx, .jpeg, .raw, .do, .bam or .fastq (Table 1). Information about the software needed to open these common files will be provided within each dataset or file.

Table 1. Summary of data generated during WHEATBIOME project life.

Data	Format
Project stakeholders' information and contacts datasets	.xlsx
Literature review, databases and outcomes of projects	.xlsx, .txt, .docx, .enl, .pdf
Protocols and questionnaires for case studies	.xlsx, .csv, .txt, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta
Meteorological and/or agronomic conditions	.xlsx, .txt, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta, .sav, .bam, .fastq
Soil physical-chemical analysis	.xlsx, .txt, .pdf, .docx
Soil and plant microbial DNA sequencing data	.bam, .fastq, .sav
Plant and food nutritional analysis	.xlsx, .txt, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta
Metabolomics and proteomics analysis	.xlsx, .raw, .txt, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta
List of microorganisms for novel food production	.xlsx, .txt, .pdf, .docx
Food components molecular interaction and food/human interaction	.xlsx, .raw, .jpeg, .txt, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta
Questionnaires and surveys	.xlsx, .csv, .jpeg, .txt, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta
Clinical trials information (body composition, blood, stool and salivary sample data or breath test data)	.xlsx, .csv
Fermented feed analysis	.xlsx, .raw, .jpeg, .txt, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta
Life Cycle Assessment	.xlsx

2.3 Making data interoperable

The depositors will strive to use commonly and internationally used metadata in their field of research, since no widely accepted specific metadata vocabularies exist. Data variable names and units, commonly accepted by the international scientific community and International System of Units, will be used. The vast majority of the datasets will be made available as spreadsheets, .xlsx format, and/or as .txt, .csv, .docx, .enl, .do, .dta, .bam or .fastq, so that they can be fully used by potential users.

2.4 Making data re-use

The project will make use, in general, of the CC-BY license. The particular license applicable to each dataset, will be decided on an individual basis, though the recommendation will be either CC-BY or CC-BY-SA.

The data will remain re-usable after the end of the project by anyone interested in it, with no access or time restrictions, since the Zenodo repository will be used. Each archived dataset will have its own permanent repository ID and will be easily accessible. We expect most of the data generated to be made available without restrictions and only datasets subject to IPR and confidentiality issues will be restricted. Where this is going to be the case, agreements will be made based on the individual datasets. Requests for the use of the data by externals will be approved by the project consortium.

Regarding data quality, since all datasets will support publication in peer-reviewed open access journals, the standards of quality (validation of the sample, replication and comparison with results of similar studies) will be met.

New data will be announced on the web page of the WHEATBIOME project <https://www.wheatbiome-project.eu/> and the different profiles in the social media, with links to the page with the dataset on Zenodo. Internally, all partners will be informed by team platforms or e-mail about the availability of new datasets, including the link to Zenodo.

3. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the management of data, WHEATBIOME beneficiaries will also manage other research outputs generated within the work plan of the project, which will be openly accessible, findable and usable (Table 2).

Table 2. WHEATBIOME Exploitation Plan

	BACKGROUND IN USE	EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	EXPLOITATION STRATEGY	IP PROTECTION
REQUIMTE	Experts in in vitro interaction studies of the human microbiome	New molecular and cell models for microbiota studies in bio-availability & -accessibility New knowledge on the oral microbiota contribution for unpleasant taste perception	Further internal, collaborative research and replication activities (Application of new models and knowledge to other projects); scientific publications	Confidentiality, Copyright
UPORTO	Experts in agronomy, edaphology, microbiology, ecotoxicology and consumer's evaluation of agri-food products	New knowledge on the cross-talk between wheat microbiome, (a)biotic factors and wheat quality New data on sensory profiling of novel fermented products	Scientific Publications; further internal and collaborative research	Copyright; confidentiality
UVIGO	Expertise in Nutrition and Food studies and analysis	Know-how on extraction methods for bioactive compounds analysis. New standardization procedures for wheat nutritional profiles	Scientific publications; networking and future joint research; and training of PhD and postdoctoral students	Copyright; confidentiality
UVEG	Expert in fermentation processes and innovative food processing technologies	New wheat-isolated microbial cultures for biotech applications	Patent licensing / Spin-off for these isolated microbials	Patent
		New knowledge on fermentation processes and recycle of wheat by-products	Scientific publications, more internal/joint research (use of new methods in other projects)	Copyright; confidentiality
IBPRS	Expertise in microbial technology, fermentation and food safety assessment	Know-how on the use of wheat by-products and impact of fermentation in feed production	Further internal research, PhD/Postdoc training, and scientific publications	Confidentiality; copyright
CTA	Expert in LCA and LCC assessments.	Know-how on conducting LCA on multiple agricultural scenarios and case studies	Replication activities & joint research (LCA & LCC services for other agro-food companies)	Trade secret

WUR	Expertise in metabolomics and proteomics analysis, especially in plant allergens and polyphenolics	New knowledge on processing methods reducing levels of immunogenic peptides in wheat	Scientific publications, internal or collaborative research, replication activities (use of new skills on other food types)	Copyright; Confidentiality
SGGW	Expert in poultry health studies	New knowledge on the impact of fermented feed on poultry health and quality of products	Scientific publications, further internal or collaborative research	Copyright; Confidentiality
		New diets that improve poultry health and quality of products	Patent licensing / Spin-off of the new poultry diets	Patent
NMS	Expert in designing and conducting clinical studies for microbiota evaluation	New knowledge on the interference of fermented product with human microbiota	Scientific publications, further internal or collaborative research	Copyright; Confidentiality
UVMB	Expertise in risk assessment and communication in food system actors & consumers	New knowledge on risk perception of food system stakeholders about microbiomes and communication approaches	Replication activities & joint research (use of risk assessment in other projects), scientific publications	Copyright; Confidentiality
EDAGRI	Expertise in communication, dissemination and organization of international events in the agro-food field	Know-how of new hybrid approaches and multimedia tactics for international events	Replication activities (application on new methodology on other projects or countries)	Confidentiality
ART21	Experts in agriculture data science and development of decision support systems	New knowledge on artificial intelligence analysis architecture and analytical algorithms	More internal/joint research & replication activities (use of DSS and APP in other fields/countries)	Trade secret; Copyright
ISANATUR	Expertise in manufacturing of food products, including functional foods	New knowledge on fermentation and processing techniques for food production	Replication activities (application of new methodology on other products or projects), further internal/collaborative research	Trade secret

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

There are no costs associated with the described mechanisms to make the database FAIR and long term preserved since we are using the Zenodo repository. Data files quality will be checked by the data manager who will be also responsible for submitting them to Zenodo. However, to ensure the widest dissemination and impact of our research findings, we recognize the importance of openly publishing supplementary material, including comprehensive details about methods and other relevant data information. As part of our commitment to open science, the project will allocate resources to support open-access publication.

The project coordinator has the ultimate responsibility for the data management in the project.

5. DATA SECURITY

On one hand, the Zenodo repository takes care of security and backup of the deposited data. On the other hand, regarding the data-sharing process involved between partners during research, Teams Online libraries associated with the O365 platform will be used, and data protection services are provided by Microsoft to prevent the loss of data, within the institutional account of the coordinator.

To ensure data security, we will follow best practices mainly for clinical trials, implementing robust provisions and SOPs for data handling. We will use a secure data store within our faculty for safe storage and archiving, particularly for participant sensitive information, to minimize data breach risks. This approach upholds ethical and regulatory requirements.

The research data will be securely stored in trusted repositories like Zenodo and ClinicalTrials.gov, ensuring long-term preservation. These reputable platforms enable accessibility and reliability beyond the project's duration, supporting future research and potential re-use.

6. ETHICS

The ethical aspects related to the personal data collected in WHEATBIOME datasets are addressed in project deliverable D9.1. Ethics principles and guidelines for protection of personal data.

As we proceed with our clinical trial, we will prioritize addressing any ethics or legal issues that may arise and could impact data sharing. We will strictly follow ethical guidelines and seek ethics review to protect participants' rights and confidentiality. Our ethical advisor will be actively consulted throughout the project to ensure ethical considerations are thoroughly addressed, especially concerning data sharing and long-term preservation. During the informed consent process, we will provide clear information about data sharing and long-term preservation.

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